

Urbanization and Global
Environmental Change

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**Addressing Grand Challenges
for Global Sustainability:**
Monitoring, Forecasting,
and Governance of Urban Systems

IHDP

International Human Dimensions Programme
on Global Environmental Change

ASU GLOBAL INSTITUTE
of SUSTAINABILITY

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Editorial

Dear friends of the UGEC project,

Urbanization is one of the most powerful, irreversible, and visible anthropogenic forces on Earth driving transformations of landscapes and ecosystems and global environmental problems. The UGEC project is committed to promoting new scientific understanding of the interactions between urban areas and global environmental change and this new understanding has begun to take shape in local governance structures. Our publications serve as important communication tools as we continue to pursue the exchange of experiences and knowledge towards sustainability pathways for urban areas. The goal of *UGEC Viewpoints*, in particular, is to communicate and facilitate the development of new directions in research and practice on urbanization and global environmental change, fostering international collaborations across disciplines and scholars/practitioners.

Notwithstanding this progress, a significant amount of work lies ahead for researchers and practitioners exploring the theme of global sustainability in an urbanizing world. The establishment of the new ICSU-supported Earth System Sustainability Initiative (ESSI) provides an opportunity for an added boost to the process of knowledge creation and application. The founding document of ESSI, 'Earth System Science for Global Sustainability: The Grand Challenges' (<http://www.icsu-visioning.org/other/grand-challenges/>) states that "[t]he international scientific community holds the promise of delivering the knowledge necessary for answering these crucial questions. But realizing that promise will require a refocusing of research priorities and a reorientation towards new research frontiers." This refocusing of research priorities led ESSI to identify five Grand Challenges in which scientific advancement and practical application needs speeding up. These challenges centrally focus on the themes of *forecasting* ("improving the usefulness of forecasts of future environmental conditions and their consequences for people"), *observing* ("developing, enhancing and integrating the observation systems needed to manage global and regional environmental change"), *confining* ("determining how to anticipate, avoid and manage disruptive global environmental change"), *responding* ("determining what institutional, economic and behavioral changes can enable effective steps toward global sustainability") and *innovating* ("encouraging innovation [...] in developing technological, policy, and social responses to achieve global sustainability").

As strong supporters of the vision of the ESSI, we highlight in this issue how the dimension of urbanization and global change fits into the envisaged objectives and scientific agenda of the ESSI Grand Challenges. The challenges posed by ESSI are areas to which UGEC project researchers and practitioners are increasingly turning their attention – the current issue of the *UGEC Viewpoints* showcases several examples. In particular, we include articles that are representative of the work occurring within the UGEC network, address three of the five major challenges posed by the ESSI, and apply them to urban systems. The authors address questions of *monitoring/observing* (Javed Mallick, Atiqur Rahman, Maik Netzband and Sunil Bhaskaran; Lucy Hutyra, Steve Raciti, Nathan Phillips and J. William Munger; Xiangrong Wang, Shixiong Wang, Yuan Wang, Huanran Ling and Zhengqiu Fan), *forecasting* (Burak Güneralp; Helber López Covaleda and Tyler Frazier) and *responding* (Anna Brown and Sam Kernaghan; JoAnn Carmin, David Dodman and Eric Chu; Mauricio Domínguez-Aguilar and Federico Dickinson Bannack; Peter Elias; B.K Singh and Shiraz Wajih). The overview article by Libby Wentz, Karen Seto, Soe Myint, Maik Netzband and Michail Fragkias, which introduces a special section of articles authored by workshop participants, summarizes the findings of the two recent jointly-held UGEC-sponsored workshops and addresses the issue of the synthesis of research on monitoring, forecasting and governance in urban systems.

We hope you enjoy reading the 6th issue of the *UGEC Viewpoints*. We greatly enjoyed putting it together!

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Michail Fragkias". The signature is fluid and cursive.

Michail Fragkias
UGEC Executive Officer

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Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Environmental Change and Urban Resilience: The Experiences of Gorakhpur

B.K Singh and Shiraz Wajih

Over the last two decades, the resilience of urban areas with respect to environmental change has been considered an issue of great importance not only at the global level but also at the national, state and even local level, due to the complex interlinkages of urban systems. In many small- and medium-sized towns in India, these systems are not only comprised of physical infrastructure, but involve complex interrelationships between social, cultural, political, institutional, economic, geographic, organizational and environmental factors. These interrelationships influence the population, their activities and their response patterns under differing conditions.

In most of the small- and medium-sized towns in Uttar Pradesh, India (one of most economically impoverished states within the country), rapid urbanization is placing substantial pressure on natural resources. Consequently, these towns are experiencing serious problems which concern the environment, urban management, poverty and development.

This article assesses the development pattern of Gorakhpur city in light of recent climatic changes. It also presents the

initiatives put forth by the Gorakhpur Environmental Action Group¹ under the guidance of the Asian Cities Climate Change Resilience Network (ACCCRN)² to develop urban resilience through community participation.

Urban growth in Gorakhpur

The city of Gorakhpur is one of the fastest growing cities in the Tarai³ belt of the Mid-Gangetic Plains of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. It has seen unprecedented growth in the last

1 <http://www.geagindia.org/>

2 The ACCCRN is supported by The Rockefeller Foundation. More information about the Network can be accessed here: <http://www.rockefellerfoundation.org/what-we-do/current-work/developing-climate-change-resilience/asian-cities-climate-change-resilience/>

3 The Tarai is a belt of marshy grassland at the base of Himalaya range in India, Nepal and Bhutan.

Figure 1 | Gorakhpur City: Temperature scenario (1991-2008)

Source: Verma, S.S., 2009

Figure 2 | Gorakhpur City: Variations in annual rainfall (1901-2008)

Source: Opitz-Stapleton, 2009

Figure 3 | Gorakhpur City: Number of rainy days (1976-2010)

Source: Wajih et al., 2010

two decades, but this has come at the cost of unmanaged urban development characterized by poor environmental governance, traffic congestion, income disparities, poor delivery of basic services, social inequalities and lack of adequate capacity to manage the effects of climate change and resulting impacts (e.g., contaminated water and health pandemics) of natural disasters (e.g., flooding and water logging) (Wajih et al., 2010). The city needs massive investments in infrastructure, public services, institutional capacity and environmental programmes if basic security, health, safety and overall conditions are to improve for the majority of urban residents.

In 2001 the city of Gorakhpur had a population of 622,701⁴ but it has now exceeded the four million mark⁵ and has an average density of about 5,882 persons/km². During the last three decades, the population of the city has increased rapidly with record growth occurring between 1981-1991(64.1 %) due to the incorporation of adjacent rural areas into the municipal area. Besides natural population growth (2.3 % per annum), migration from nearby rural areas, as well as from outside the state to the city, has been a prominent factor influencing the ongoing rapid urban demographic growth and has exerted tremendous pressure on the land, water and varying infrastructural facilities. This has led to the development of numerous slums and informal sectors within the city, where inhabitants face living conditions that deteriorate further with each passing day. Currently, 33 percent of the city’s population is concentrated in 110 slums located within the city boundary.

Changing climate

Global environmental change is a function of complex interwoven factors, but when analyzed at the micro level it is quite apparent that its varying impacts are very much localized. The rapid concentration of urban population and mercurial nature of the monsoon in south and southeast Gorakhpur have already made this region more vulnerable. The recent climate induced calamities have added a new layer of complexity, forcing policy makers and planners to retrospectively assess the development scenarios of these areas (Wajih et al., 2010). However, the lack of data availability on climate change within the public domain bottlenecks the formulization of any concrete planning to cope with its adverse impacts.

Historically, the climate of Gorakhpur and its surrounding areas has been mild (Nevill, 1909). However, in last few years there has been a rapid alteration and unexpected changes in the

4 http://www.censusindia.gov.in/towns/up_towns.pdf (Last accessed on August 4, 2011)

5 http://censusindia.gov.in/2011-prov-results/paper2/data_files/UP/datasheetpaper2.pdf (Last accessed on August 4, 2011)

temperature pattern, rainfall amount and moisture content in the air. The number of days above 40° Celsius/104° Fahrenheit is increasing each year and there has been a 9.51 percent increase in the maximum temperature during 2003 and 2008. However, at the opposite end, the annual minimum temperature has recorded a decreasing trend (Verma, 2009) (see Figure1). This aberration in temperature has raised several questions around whether these changes are attributable to the impact of global climatic change or the phenomenon of localized climatic altering. Despite the fact that there is no conclusive evidence that these shifts are the outcome of anthropogenic climatic change, the citizens of Gorakhpur are nevertheless feeling the effects of such changes (Opitz–Stapleton, 2010).

More rainfall in fewer days

The changing temperature has also affected the rainfall pattern and moisture content in the city’s atmosphere creating considerable variation in annual rainfall. Since 2004, the trend shows a continual increase in rainfall (see Figure 2), however, while the rainfall amount is increasing, in Gorakhpur the number of rainfall days has decreased (see Figure 3). Due to low capacity of water storage and poor solid waste management and sanitation systems, this increased intensity of rainfall has exacerbated water logging and constricts the mobility within the city.

Water logging and flooding

There are many factors which contribute to the city’s problems of flooding and water logging. The saucer shaped topography and gentle slope is less equipped to handle increasing water flows from Nepal into the rivers Rapti and Rohin. This along with other factors, such as the degradation of water bodies, unplanned development, poor infrastructure, localized underground sewerage and a lack of solid waste management further exasperate the problem (Wajih et al., 2009). During the last few decades, water logging has become chronic in many parts of the city and if development continues without modification, it can be easily predicted that the people of Gorakhpur will face serious consequences in terms of their health and livelihoods. At present, 18 percent of the city (see Figure 4), especially the southern, western and central areas, face acute water logging (Wajih et al., 2009). In these areas water remains stagnant for more than three to four months, creating serious health conditions and the increase of health hazards.

Sewerage and solid waste

The coverage of a sewage network in Gorakhpur is very poor. Presently, only 22 percent of the total area is covered by an underground sewer network (Wajih et al., 2009). The existing

Figure 4 | Gorakhpur City: Water logged area, 2008

Map prepared by GEAG on Universal Transverse Mercator – Zone 44 (N)World Geodetic 1984 (WGS84) in 2010

Source: Wajih et al., 2010

Figure 5 | Gorakhpur City: The risk frame

Source: Wajih et al., 2009

sewage networks cater primarily to the older areas of the city area. Since the city has no sewage treatment plant, sewage is directly released either into the river or into water reservoirs, leading to further pollution and increasing siltation of river beds. Due to improper maintenance, most of the open drains are badly damaged and choked with silt and garbage. Furthermore, a poor solid waste management system has perpetuated the problem of water logging. Due to a lack of formal dumping sites, all garbage is disposed of either along roads or used as land fill material within low-lying areas.

Vulnerability

The perpetuation of water logging and flooding in the city cannot be attributed to any single factor, rather it is attributed to a combination of different risks (i.e., natural/topographical, behavioral and governance) (see Figure 5). While, the problem of solid waste management and localized sewage has its own negative effects in the form of disease and health risks, it also aggravates the situation of water logging. Thus, the causal factors are interdependent and interrelated in influencing the vulnerability of the city. The risk of water logging in Gorakhpur is increasing every year, damaging the infrastructure and affecting the society as a whole, particularly the underprivileged who are the city’s most vulnerable, as they have neither the capacity to respond nor the option of moving to safer locations.

Resilience strategy approach

Practically speaking, resilience development within the city system and amongst people is a slow process. Under the guidance of the Asian Cities Climate Change Resilience Network (ACCCRN), the Gorakhpur Environmental Action Group has evolved a resilience framework and formulated a strategy that considers the interconnectedness of three risk categories within the city of Gorakhpur (i.e., natural, behavioral and governance) for increasing the city’s resilience to climate change. The strategy advocates that resilience development cannot be achieved through just a single intervention point, but requires an integrated approach. The basic concept behind the strategy is the proactive role on part of the government in developing the resilience of the city, while citizens must likewise be organized and ready to take ownership and partnership in the city’s development towards resilience.

This concept, (see Figure 6) emphasizes the behavioral aspects along the outer circle, while the inner core addresses the physical, infrastructural, and governance components. It is believed that

Figure 6 | Resilience strategy

Source: Wajih et al., 2010

the strengthening of behavioral aspects (circle of influence) through awareness will positively influence the inner core (circle of concern, i.e., system) to become more responsive, transparent and accountable. This will in turn aid in the development of a citizen–government synergy for the development of the city and its resilience capacities over the long term.

Strategy for moving ahead

As stated, resilience cannot be achieved through a single intervention point. The strategy created for Gorakhpur advocates integrated courses of action to address a combination of institutional, behavioral, social and technical issues. Hence, the areas identified for strengthening resilience vis a vis vulnerable sectors and respective actions can be summarized in Table 1.

Conclusion

Thus, to develop resilience in an urban system and achieve sustainability, it is essential to adopt a multi-pronged, multi-scale strategy targeting diverse groups and stakeholders; this type of approach speaks to the complexity of the urban system and addresses those factors of which it is comprised (i.e., natural, behavioral, governance, institutional and political). An urban developmental plan should be prepared on the basis of real-time facts and information rather than projected data. Additionally, it is also requisite to develop proper coordination amongst associated departments on their development agendas before such a plan becomes implemented. Lastly, it cannot be stressed enough that there must be extensive interplay between the system and the people, as this is pivotal in making both entities accountable and responsive to the impacts of environmental change.

Table 1 | Identified actions for strengthening resilience

Vulnerable Sectors	Areas to Strengthen Resilience	Actions
Housing	Effective master planning and proper enforcement	Ward-level micro-resilience plan developed and institutionalized review of master plan
	Awareness among citizens	
	Water harvesting	
Industries and commerce	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) measures	Sensitization of industries and commercial establishments for EIAs, energy efficiency, waste management and organized housing
	Effective monitoring of waste treatment	
	Organized housing for industrial workers	
Basic services	Quality of drinking water monitoring and awareness generation	Establishing multiple channels for data collection and reporting on water quality
	Effective drainage system according to geo-hydrology of the city	Making the proposed drainage system more effective and energy efficient
	Decentralized community-owned solid waste management	Designing a city-wide community-based Solid Waste Management (SWM) system based on a pilot Public-Private-Community Participation (PPCP) model
Transportation	Planned transport system for the city	Designing for a green and resilient transport system for the city
	Public transport system to be enhanced	
	Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) vehicles to be introduced	
Energy / Electricity	Alternate energy sources	Sensitizing industries and commercial establishments to adopt energy efficient measures
	Conversion to Compact Fluorescent Lightbulbs (CFL) in private and public places	
Health	Effective health surveillance system	Establishing a city-wide health surveillance system
	Preventive health measures	Identifying and promoting preventive health measures and practices for water and vector borne diseases
	Sensitization and education	
Ecosystem	Conservation of water bodies	Mapping, demarcation and conservation
	Plantation and public land to be protected	Promoting plantation public land
	Sensitization and awareness	School education programmes

Source: Wajih, et al. (2010)

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